

AugmentedWearEdu: Pioneering Haptic Integration in E-Learning with an Open-Source Platform

Leonardo Franco¹, Gionata Salvietti^{1,2}

Abstract—AugmentedWearEdu, an Erasmus+ European initiative, is devoted to enhancing immersive education by supplying educators with reasonably priced and open-source VR solutions. The project’s open-source framework simplifies customization to accommodate individual teaching requirements and subject demands. One of the technological outputs of the project is SimpleThimble, a wearable haptic device that can give force feedback to the fingertips. Emphasizing simplicity and affordability, we designed SimpleThimble for easy assembly without requiring specialized tools or technical expertise. It seamlessly integrates with the Unity development platform, enabling adaptation to various virtual world applications. The project website provides downloadable 3D models, facilitating users to acquire the necessary components through 3D printing, whether at home or in a laboratory. What distinguishes this project is its capability to equip educators with a wide-ranging skill set, from programming to 3D printing, enhancing the learning experience with wearable haptics technology and its virtual reality applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education plays a crucial role in shaping the intellectual and practical skills of individuals and contributes to their overall development [1]. Traditional approaches to education have relied predominantly on visual and auditory stimuli as the primary means of conveying information and promoting learning.

However, the advent of innovative technologies and research on the subject has highlighted the importance of haptics, the sense of touch, in enhancing educational experiences [2]. Haptics provides a unique way for learners to engage with their environment, enabling them to explore, manipulate and understand concepts more effectively. This article aims to highlight the importance of haptics in education and its potential to innovate education by providing immersive and multi-sensory learning experiences.

The growing recognition of the significance of haptics in education sets the stage for the AugmentedWearEdu project, in which we have developed the SimpleThimble depicted in Fig. 1, a wearable haptic thimble. In the following sections, we will present the features and capabilities of the SimpleThimble as an integral component of our framework for enhancing e-learning experiences in laboratory settings.

II. THE PROJECT

A. Haptics, VR and education: AugmentedWearEdu

The SimpleThimble was conceptualized in the context of AugmentedWearEdu, a project co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union. The main objective of

Fig. 1: The SimpleThimble mechanics in a CAD view. The outer part is in transparency to let the reader see the rack and pinion mechanism responsible for the vertical shift of the fingertip pad.

AugmentedWearEdu is to introduce a novel framework for e-learning that consists of incorporating haptic experiences to enable digital access to laboratories in higher education. This will be achieved by combining both Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) tools with a new generation of wearable haptic devices. This will enable students to engage in a haptic-audio-visual hands-on laboratory environment. This project will evaluate which of the available haptic technologies are suitable for e-learning and can enhance students’ ability to create complex simulations using existing or in-world modelling techniques and scripting tools, while providing the functionality to link to the real world and capture data that can be visualised in real time. Haptics, VR and AR tools will be adopted either from our ongoing research activities or from various low-cost commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) tools. This will also create an innovative education and research loop. This approach will contribute to the realisation of fully immersive, open and distance laboratory learning.

AugmentedWearEdu is revolutionising e-learning in STEM disciplines by providing a comprehensive toolkit for creating immersive augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR) courses. Our initiative, showcased on the AugmentedWearEdu web portal, enables educators to harness the full potential of hands-on modules in STEM labs. By combining off-the-shelf components, our platform facilitates the development of a wearable haptic interface that enables haptic interaction in VR/AR e-learning experiences.

¹ are with the Department of Information Engineering and Mathematics, University of Siena, Siena, Italy. {leonardo.franco2, gionata.salvietti}@unisi.it

² is with the Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Genova, Italy.

Fig. 2: A screenshot taken from the ReadTheDocs documentation website in which the reader and haptics students can find all the resources to build for themselves and program a pair of SimpleThimbles.

To our knowledge, the AugmentedWearEdu Portal represents the first initiative to provide both open software and hardware tools for designing innovative hands-on courses. By integrating VR/AR technologies with wearable haptic interfaces, we unlock the potential for immersive lab experiences within e-Learning platforms.

In line with the growing recognition of haptics in education, it is worth mentioning the work of Allison Okamura at Stanford University. She has developed a course that utilizes an open-source grounded haptic interface called the Hapkit [3], [4]. This exemplifies the ongoing efforts of researchers and educators to explore haptics as a valuable tool in enhancing the learning experience. Our AugmentedWearEdu project further contributes to this field by providing educators with the necessary tools to create their own customized courses, enabling them to leverage wearable haptic interfaces in conjunction with VR/AR technologies. This empowers educators to design innovative hands-on experiences within e-learning platforms and represents a significant paradigm shift in engineering education, making laboratory experiments more accessible and engaging for students.

B. The SimpleThimble device and its online resources

To create a compelling wearable haptic experience, designers must carefully consider three essential elements: a well-designed wearable device that can effectively generate and deliver haptic feedback, a virtual reality (VR) application enabling users to interact with 3D objects and environments for an immersive haptic experience, and accurate hand tracking technology to capture users' hand movements and facilitate intuitive haptic interactions with virtual content. By successfully integrating these elements, designers can ensure the development of a satisfying wearable haptic experience. In the case of SimpleThimble

we aimed at ease of build and accessibility of items to build it as priorities. All components can be mounted without a screw and most of its parts are 3D printable. All 3D files to build the mechanical parts of the thimble are available for free at the website <https://simplethimble.readthedocs.io/>. From a mechanical point of view the SimpleThimble is made of a motor which provides the single degree of freedom of the single thimble, a rack and pinion mechanism highlighted in Fig. 1, in which the rack has a specialized shape to cover in an ergonomic way the fingertip, and few other part such as neoprene tape and velcro strips. At the core of the thimble there is an ESP microcontroller of Espressif semiconductor company. This microcontroller enabled us to connect easily the motors of the thimbles wirelessly, and also to charge a battery which the user can wear together with the microcontroller on its wrist. The ESP D1 mini module that we chose is user-friendly since online is full of support to program it, and we also did a basic guide which let the use learn in a self-paced experience how to program such microcontrollers. Moreover, this specific board footprint supports a shield which hosts a battery charger unit on board.

We made a tutorial on the aforementioned SimpleThimble website which guides the user to install all the necessary software components to build their own Unity VR project. The tutorial that is present in the website is made to interact with a virtual red cube by using two SimpleThimbles worn in the thumb and in the index finger as shown in Fig. 2. The tracking of the hand is performed by using the Leap Motion, an optical markerless tracker specialized to track hands movements and be light and portable.

III. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the AugmentedWearEdu project, with its flagship component, the SimpleThimble, represents a pioneering advance in e-learning. By providing educators with open software and hardware tools, this framework enables the design of immersive and hands-on courses. The integration of VR/AR technologies with the SimpleThimble's wearable haptic interface revolutionises the delivery of laboratory experiences, empowering learners and increasing engagement while fostering practical skills development. This innovative approach has huge potential to transform education across a range of disciplines, marking a new era of interactive and impactful learning experiences.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Minogue and M. G. Jones, "Haptics in education: Exploring an untapped sensory modality," *Review of Educational Research*, vol. 76, no. 3, pp. 317–348, 2006.
- [2] K. J. Schönborn, P. Bivall, and L. A. Tibell, "Exploring relationships between students' interaction and learning with a haptic virtual biomolecular model," *Computers & Education*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 2095–2105, 2011.
- [3] T. K. Morimoto, P. Blikstein, and A. M. Okamura, "[d81] hapkit: An open-hardware haptic device for online education," in *2014 IEEE Haptics Symposium (HAPTICS)*. IEEE, 2014, pp. 1–1.
- [4] T. Morimoto, M. O. Martinez, R. Davis, P. Blikstein, and A. M. Okamura, "Teaching with hapkit: Enabling online haptics courses with hands-on laboratories," *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 79–91, 2020.